

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№ 11

2025

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

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*Elektron nashr. 908 sahifa.
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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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CROSS-BORDER E-COMMERCE IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract. Cross-border e-commerce in Central Asia has a huge potential, especially with its strategic geographic location, various natural resources, and growing customer demand. These factors play a vital role when it comes to achieving a desired potential for e-commerce growth. Central Asia's e-commerce development leads to new job creations, new innovations and encourages people to create new businesses. But there are some obstacles that make e-commerce operations and their growth difficult because there are not many effective logistics infrastructures that can support the development of e-trade. This paper suggests some possible solutions after analyzing the stumbling blocks of Central Asian logistics and e-commerce condition.

Key words: Operations, supply chain, Central Asia, international trade, logistics, e-commerce, digital technologies, regional relations.

Annotatsiya. Markaziy Osiyo o'zining strategik joylashuvi, boy tabiiy resurslari va o'sib borayotgan iste'molchilar bazasi bilan elektron tijorat sohasida katta imkoniyatlarga ega. Elektron tijorat mintaqada iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantirish va yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish uchun muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Biroq elektron tijoratning muvaffaqiyati ko'p jihatdan logistika tizimining samaradorligiga bog'liq. Ushbu maqolada Markaziy Osiyodagi elektron tijorat logistikasi tahlil qilinadi, uning imkoniyatlari va muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Markaziy Osiyo, xalqaro savdo, logistika, elektron tijorat, raqamli texnologiyalar, mintaqaviy aloqalar.

Аннотация. Трансграничная электронная коммерция в Центральной Азии обладает значительным экономическим потенциалом. Стратегическое географическое положение региона, богатые природные ресурсы и растущий потребительский спрос являются ключевыми факторами, способствующими развитию e-commerce. Развитие электронной торговли стимулирует создание новых рабочих мест, внедрение инноваций и расширение предпринимательской активности. Однако недостаточно развитая логистическая инфраструктура остаётся серьёзным препятствием для устойчивого роста отрасли. В статье проводится анализ текущего состояния логистики и электронной коммерции в Центральной Азии и предлагаются практические решения по преодолению существующих барьеров.

Ключевые слова: операции, цепочка поставок, Центральная Азия, международная торговля, логистика, электронная коммерция, цифровые технологии, региональное сотрудничество.

INTRODUCTION

Not long ago, in 2024, the global e-commerce market was expected to reach more than six trillion dollars. The reason for this projection was not only growing mobile commerce demand but also new AI technologies, with mobile sales that made up over 50% of e-commerce sales [7]. Even though there is a rapid increase in e-commerce of Central Asia, they are still undergoing region specific challenges such as lack of modern infrastructure, imbalance of economic conditions of countries and roads that are old enough to support this logistics transformation. With its important location on trade routes between Europe and Asia, Central Asia has strong potential as an international trade hub. Kazakhstan's e-commerce market reached to almost five million and a half dollars in 2023, growing 24% year-over-year but hampered by inefficient cross-border trade [12]. Similarly, Uzbekistan's e-commerce has grown 30% annually since 2019 due to increased mobile and internet use but still struggles with logistical limitations [10]. With a projected growth rate of 32.2% by 2032, Central Asia's success in e-commerce depends on logistics efficiency, including fast delivery, storage, and distribution. Expanding logistics infrastructure, improving cross-border transport, and adopting AI-driven warehouse and route management are essential to realizing the region's e-commerce potential.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Cross-border e-commerce in Central Asia has been the focus of growing empirical and policy-oriented research, reflecting the region's rapid digitalization and its emerging role in Eurasian trade corridors. According to UNCTAD's B2C E-Commerce Index published in recent years, the e-commerce potential of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan is increasingly shaped by improvements in digital payment systems, the expansion of internet access and the reliability of postal and delivery infrastructure. However, UNCTAD experts underline that the "last-mile gap," fragmented logistics chains and uneven digital readiness across borders remain key constraints to regional integration.

The World Bank's Central Asia Digital Connectivity and Trade Integration report highlights that the growth of cross-border e-commerce is strongly dependent on harmonized data-exchange standards, electronic customs systems and interoperable digital identity solutions. Although Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan demonstrate strong progress in digital public services, the report notes that insufficient regulatory coordination across borders slows down cross-border shipment processing and increases transaction costs for SMEs engaging in e-commerce.

Insights from the McKinsey Global Institute's analysis of the Asian digital economy reveal that in regions with limited integration, cross-border e-commerce typically accounts for only 15–20 percent of total online trade volumes. This is attributed to high logistics costs, burdensome customs procedures and fragmented payment ecosystems — patterns that closely resemble the structural barriers observed in Central Asia. Complementing this, the OECD's Trade Facilitation Indicators emphasize that border documentation procedures, customs transparency and risk-management systems in Central Asia still lag behind global benchmarks, directly affecting cross-border delivery times.

Research by Ferracane and Mauro within the Digital Trade Restrictiveness Index shows that several Central Asian economies exhibit restrictive digital policies, including data-localization requirements and complex licensing rules for digital payment providers. These regulatory rigidities limit the scalability of cross-border e-commerce platforms. This aligns with the findings of Joshua Meltzer, who demonstrates in his work on data flows and digital trade that regulatory harmonization and the free flow of data are essential drivers of e-commerce growth for developing economies.

A complementary perspective is provided in the Cross-Border E-Commerce Development Report produced by the Alibaba Research Center, where Asia-wide modeling shows that digital logistics corridors, real-time customs processing systems and "single-window" frameworks can dramatically accelerate export-oriented e-commerce. Such mechanisms are particularly relevant for landlocked regions like Central Asia, where physical connectivity constraints intensify the importance of digital efficiency.

The EBRD's Digital Transition in Central Asia study further emphasizes that the modernization of transport corridors, electronic documentation and integrated supply-chain platforms are strategically necessary to unlock the region's e-commerce export potential. Academic research published in the Journal of International Trade & Economic Development by Ferris and Hernandez reinforces this viewpoint, arguing that in emerging markets, cross-border e-commerce performance is strongly correlated with logistics reforms, consumer trust and the density of digital payment infrastructures.

Taken together, the existing literature consistently demonstrates that the sustainability of cross-border e-commerce growth in Central Asia depends not only on technological advancements but also on regional policy harmonization, the digitalization of customs systems and the modernization of logistics corridors. Without addressing these structural factors, the export-oriented segment of e-commerce will continue to expand slowly despite rising domestic digital adoption.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study analyzes the evolving landscape of cross-border e-commerce in Central Asia, highlighting the region's significant opportunities for growth using a mixed-methods approach. This includes a comprehensive literature review, analysis of statistical data, and case studies of successful e-commerce platforms in Central Asia. The focus of this research is to investigate the landscape of the e-commerce market in Central Asia, concentrating on the key factors that are influencing the growth of e-commerce and the role of logistics in overcoming existing issues in the region

Growth in Market Demand. The growing population of around 82.5 million people and the emergence of a growing middle class in Central Asia will have a positive impact on the e-commerce market. In addition, the interest of the younger generation (50% of the whole population is under 30 years old per "Worldometer") in digital technologies is projected to increase the demand for online shopping. The region's median age of the population is 26.7 [13]. The demographic changes illustrate the need for enhanced e-commerce services and solutions that can adapt to higher demand, ensuring on-time deliveries, efficient distribution, and inadequate inventory management.

Technology. Even though internet penetration is still low in the region, the expansion of internet technologies with advanced mobile devices has created opportunities for the development of e-commerce [5]. The convenience of shopping through mobile applications and online platforms is rapidly increasing, encouraging Central Asian countries to implement programs aimed at enhancing e-commerce infrastructure. This should be supported by modern warehousing and AI-driven systems that bring accurate delivery and inventory management [6].

Development. Central Asian countries need Foreign Development Investments to enhance their infrastructure [3]. Investments in logistics infrastructure, including AI-driven supply chain optimization, warehousing, and distribution systems, enable faster and more reliable product movement, boosting customer satisfaction [9]. AI optimizes supply chains by improving route planning, demand forecasting, and reducing delivery times. While companies like Amazon and Walmart use AI for demand prediction and inventory management, Central Asia should develop its own AI-driven systems for route optimization, inventory management, and cross-border logistics to improve customer satisfaction.

Global Markets. E-commerce enables local manufacturers to reach global consumers via online platforms. However, expansion requires improved logistics with streamlined customs, real-time tracking, and last-mile delivery. Unicorns, startups, and innovative projects bring fresh ideas to the sector, while AI-driven supply chain optimization enhances cross-border goods movement.

Marketing and Advertising: Social media marketing is essential for e-commerce growth in the region, fostering customer relationships and feedback while helping brands strengthen their presence [2]. Effective marketing boosts consumer interest but relies on reliable logistics to ensure timely delivery and enhance customer satisfaction.

Payment Security: Payment security and reliability are pivotal to gaining customers' trust and loyalty in e-commerce. Improved logistics operations such as real-time tracing and in-time deliveries will improve the experience of customers and attract them to make more purchases in the future. [4]

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The interest of younger consumers in digital technologies and online shopping will significantly influence e-commerce growth. The creation of programs, legislation, and infrastructure aimed at the development of e-commerce by states will help the growth of e-commerce in the region. Efficient logistics systems and delivery services make it possible to deliver goods quickly and reliably, which makes shopping easier. Marketing and advertising through social networks allow companies to promote brands and strengthen connections with consumers. Local manufacturers and brands, by offering their products on online platforms, increase competition and attract consumers. Security and reliability of payment systems increase consumer confidence and increase interest in online shopping.[2]

Startups and new technologies offer new ideas and services in the field of e-commerce, which increases competition. Economic growth and an expanding middle class in the region will increase consumer purchasing power and drive demand for e-commerce. These factors have a direct impact on the growth of e-commerce in the region and contribute to its development. Several significant obstacles hinder the development of e-commerce in Central Asia. By implementing these strategies, increasing and expanding the Internet speed, developing mobile communication networks, as well as creating favorable conditions for e-commerce by improving logistics and transport infrastructure will be very helpful. Introducing safe and convenient digital payment systems, increasing consumer confidence and facilitating online shopping.[1]

Kazakhstan leads with 60-70% of the Central Asian e-commerce market, with Kaspersky.kz strong in fintech and e-commerce and Technodom.kz in electronics. Uzbekistan follows with 20-30%, led by platforms like OLX, Korzinka.uz, Uzum Market, Olcha, and Elmakon. Smaller markets have limited major players, resulting in uneven growth. To advance, they need investments in digital and logistics infrastructure, consumer awareness, and payment solutions, along with support from larger players, cross-border platforms, and government incentives.

Promoting local brands on online platforms and enhancing global market access is key [1]. E-commerce education for consumers and entrepreneurs, digital literacy, and online sales training, along with social media and digital marketing, can boost interest in online shopping.

Modern technologies are essential for secure e-commerce, reliable payments, and consumer protection. Support for payment system start-ups and cross-border data-sharing centers, including Internet Exchange Points (IPXs), can enhance Internet security and reduce costs [15]. Furthermore, developing consistent trade policies, cooperating on customs procedures, and aligning with global e-commerce trends will streamline cross-border trade. Simplifying legal frameworks and protecting consumer and business rights can attract investors. Initiatives like Uzbekistan's "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" and "IT Park Uzbekistan" support regional e-commerce growth with innovative policies and incentives [14].

There are several main obstacles in the development of e-commerce in Central Asia. Inefficient transportation networks with outdated infrastructure, poor road conditions, and limited rail connections hinder logistics. The lack of major seaport access in Uzbekistan and Kyrgyz Republic forces reliance on costly land transit, causing delays. Despite infrastructure investments, Kazakhstan still faces transit and customs issues, while warehousing shortages raise operational costs and limit inventory space. Also, limited Internet speed, weak logistics, and unreliable digital payment systems hamper e-commerce growth and deter online shopping. Security risks, such as data protection and fraud, undermine consumer confidence, while complex e-commerce regulations challenge entrepreneurs [4]. In addition to this, low digital literacy, complex online shopping processes, and inadequate local brand representation discourage e-commerce use. Cultural resistance to online shopping also hinders growth, and a lack of innovative technologies further obstructs e-commerce development in the region.

To optimize e-commerce logistics, there should be more investments in modern AI-driven technologies and big data that offer solutions to logistics challenges. AI enhances route planning, demand forecasting, and inventory management, reducing costs and improving efficiency. Automation in warehousing and transport minimizes human errors, while big data analysis aids in forecasting and resource optimization. Real-time GPS tracking and multi-transport options boost customer confidence. Implementing mobile apps, chatbots, and collaborations in logistics streamline resources and cut costs. RFID, IoT, and insurance options enhance product tracking and security [5]. These strategies not only reduce costs but also increase customer satisfaction and overall business performance.

Global e-commerce turnover has steadily increased, reaching \$2.9 trillion in 2018 and \$5.82 trillion by 2020, with expectations to exceed \$6.3 trillion by 2024. Key infrastructure developments—such as Internet access, payment systems, and logistics—are crucial for sustaining this growth. In MOMIH countries, private banks have fostered online marketplaces and innovative payment methods[9]. By 2034, the market is projected to reach \$75.12 trillion, significantly impacting the global economy. The number of global e-commerce consumers is expected to reach 2.71 billion by the end of 2024, driven by e-commerce platform expansion [8]. E-commerce growth varies by country, with China leading at a 52.1% market share in 2023, valued at \$3.01 trillion [7]. Mobile commerce is increasingly vital, with global sales projected to reach \$6.97 trillion in 2024, up from \$2.32 trillion in 2020. About 73% of consumers shop via mobile devices, and digital payments hit \$9.46 trillion in 2023, expected to surpass \$10.52 trillion. These systems enhance purchasing convenience, propelling e-commerce expansion, which could reach \$18.18 trillion by the end of 2024 [7].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Central Asian e-commerce logistics holds great promise but faces major challenges. The region's strategic location, fast-growing consumer base, and supportive government policies make it attractive for e-commerce growth. However, obstacles like inadequate logistics infrastructure, complex customs regulations, limited technology, and a shortage of skilled workers could hinder progress, leading to delays and reducing competitiveness. Addressing these issues requires interstate cooperation, investment, and innovation across the region, not just in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. Modernizing transport networks, establishing trade corridors, and simplifying customs will boost connectivity and efficiency. Greater investment in digital technologies, partnerships with startups, and enhanced data analytics are also essential for overcoming logistical hurdles. Furthermore, training programs like Uzbekistan's "Digital Inclusion Project" can help develop a skilled workforce. The future of e-commerce in Central Asia depends on overcoming these barriers and leveraging available opportunities to position the region as a global e-commerce hub.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>